

Mental Health and Academic Outcomes: Evidence from Honors College Students

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Abstract: This paper explores the relationship between mental health and post-secondary student outcomes. To do this, we rely on a unique dataset with information on honors students' academic performance and their mental health. Results suggest that reporting a mental health event during college has a large, negative effect on cumulative college grade point average and the probability a student is in good academic standing. Additionally, the effect size is larger for both outcomes for students who began school after the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Mental Health, Education, COVID-19

1. Introduction

Mental illness among college students is a growing concern. According to the recent study, which interviewed 350,000 students at 373 campuses between 2013 and 2021, 60 percent of students suffer from mental health problems as of 2021, a nearly 50 percent jump from 2013 (Lipson et al., 2022). The consequences of mental illnesses are wide ranging, impacting everything from heart diseases (Firth et al., 2019), wages (Evensen et al., 2017), long term welfare benefits (Homlong et al., 2015), sick-leave (de Ridder et al., 2015), to employment (Egan et al., 2015). It also impacts academic outcomes, which is the focus of this paper.

For adolescents, mental illness is associated with lower educational attainment (Cornaglia et al., 2012; Hale and Viner, 2018; Låftman and Magnusson, 2017; Melkevik et al., 2016; Plenty et al., 2021; Sagatun et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2021). For college students, the research is more limited, but there is evidence that psychosocial factors broadly are associated with a lower grade point average (Richardson et al., 2012); while depression and anxiety are associated with lower college grade point average and higher risk of dropping out (Eisenberg et al., 2009). This paper adds to the existing literature in two ways. First, it considers college students enrolled in an honors program. This demographic has been studied considerably less often than their adolescent counterparts, and they may have unique characteristics that make their response to mental health concerns unique. This paper also studies the compounding impact of Covid-19 on the relationship between

academic performance and psychological well-being, a factor that has not yet been looked at.

The empirical results suggest that reporting a mental health event during college has a large, negative effect on cumulative college grade point average (CCGPA) and the probability a student is in good standing. For both outcomes, the effect size is larger for students who began college after the Covid-19 pandemic began.

2. Data

Data come from a mid-sized, private, non-profit university in a major American city. The sample spans the 2018-2021 academic years and is comprised of all students from the university’s honors college. The dataset contains information on student standing, CCGPA, major choice, high school GPA, place of origin, and gender. Data also contain two variables related to mental health. The first, *Mental_Health_Prior*, is an indicator variable equal to 1 if a student mentions mental health concerns in their admission application. The second, *Mental_Health* is an indicator variable equal to 1 if a student mentions a mental health concern to their advisor at some point after starting college.

3. Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 displays summary statistics for all variables used in this study. These averages are split into two groups: students who mention mental health concerns while in college (*Column (1)*) and those who do not (*Column (2)*). *Column (3)* displays the difference between *Columns (1)* and *(2)*, while *Column (4)* reports a p-value for a difference in means test. Academic outcomes, ability, and baseline mental health are significantly better for students who do not reveal mental health concerns during college.

Table 1: Outcomes and Characteristics for Students Who Do and Do Not Mention Mental Health Concerns

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	MH Mention	No MH Mention	Difference	p-value
Mental Health (Before Start)	0.474	0.371	0.103	0.006
	0.500	0.484		
Good Standing	0.686	0.898	-0.212	0.000
	0.465	0.303		
College GPA	3.562	3.774	-0.212	0.000
	0.586	0.240		
High School GPA	91.310	93.079	-1.769	0.025
	13.095	7.875		
SAT Score	1356.824	1355.830	0.994	0.884
	66.665	69.668		

Table 1 continued

International Student	0.014	0.021	-0.007	0.490
	0.117	0.143		
Local Student	0.443	0.424	0.018	0.629
	0.498	0.495		
Female Student	0.786	0.748	0.038	0.245
	0.411	0.435		

Notes: Column (1) shows summary statistics for students who mention mental health concerns while in college. Column (2) shows summary statistics for students who do not. Column (3) displays the difference between Columns(1) and (2). Column (4) reports a p-value for a difference in means test.

It is also important to note the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic that occurred during the sample period. This might have put additional strain on students, increasing their susceptibility to mental health crises or amplifying the effect of them on students’ academic performance. Indeed, from *Figure 1, Panel (A)*, pre-college mental health mentions peak in 2020, when the pandemic occurred. Furthermore, in both *Figure 1, Panels (A) and (B)*, both pre- and post-enrollment mental health mentions fall substantially in 2021, indicating the return to a more normal way of life may have eased mental health pressures. *Panels (C) and (D)* tell a similar story. Here, CCGPA and student standing were at their lowest in 2020; but, like mental health, they both recovered in 2021.

Figure 1: Mental Health And Student Outcomes Over Time

Note: Panel (A) shows the proportion of students by cohort who mention mental health concerns before starting college Panel (B) shows the proportion of students by cohort who mention mental health concerns after starting college. Panel (C) shows cumulative college GPA by cohort. Panel (D) shows proportion of students in good standing by cohort.

4. Empirical Model

Estimation of the effect of mental health concerns on student outcomes relies on a fixed effects model and a pooled cross-section of students:

$$Y_{ist} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Mental_Health}_{ist} + \beta_2 \text{Mental_Health_Prior}_{ist} + X_{ist} + \gamma_t + \delta_s \quad (1)$$

Y is either CCGPA or a dummy variable for student status, where status is 1 if they are in good standing and 0 if they drop out, do not finish their thesis, or if their CCGPA falls below 3.3. *Mental_Health*, the variable of interest, and *Mental_Health_Prior*, a control for baseline mental health, are as previously defined. X is a vector of controls including high school GPA, SAT score, an indicator for whether a student is international, an indicator for whether a student is local, and an indicator for gender. γ is a year/cohort fixed effect. δ is a school fixed effect.

4. Results

Table 2 displays estimates of equation (1). Panel (A) uses CCGPA as the dependent variable. Panel (B) uses student status as the dependent variable. Each column represents a separate regression, the first three of which control for baseline ability in different ways. Column (1) uses high school GPA, Column (2) uses SAT score, and Column (3) uses both high school GPA and SAT score.¹ In all cases, the coefficient on *Mental_Health* is large, negative, and highly statistically significant. This indicates that students who report a mental health event during college are expected to see their CCGPA fall by 0.186 to 0.230 points and their probability of being in good standing decrease by approximately 18.7 to 22.0 percentage points.

In both panels, *Columns (4) and (5)* explore the possibility of heterogeneous treatment effects before and after the start of the Covid-19 pandemic. To do this, *Column (4)* restricts the sample to students who began before the 2020 academic year, while *Column (5)* restricts the sample to students who started in either 2020 or 2021. Both *Columns (4) and (5)* control for ability with high school GPA alone for the sake of statistical power. The coefficient on *Mental_Health* is large, negative, and highly statistically significant for both sub-samples and for both outcome variables. It is also substantially larger after Covid-19 pandemic began, suggesting it may have increased susceptibility to mental health crises or amplified the effect of them.

¹Not all students take the SAT exam. This is why the specifications using this as a control have a smaller sample size.

Table 2: Impact of Any Mental Health Mention on Student Outcomes, Unrestricted Sample

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
				Before Covid	After Covid
Panel (A) – Dependent Variable: CCGPA					
Mental Health (After Start)	-0.230*** (0.036)	-0.220*** (0.050)	-0.186*** (0.047)	-0.181*** (0.040)	-0.252*** (0.058)
Mental Health (Before Start)	-0.064** (0.032)	-0.072 (0.046)	-0.071 (0.045)	-0.104** (0.042)	-0.011 (0.052)
Observations	706	414	414	349	357
R-squared	0.107	0.101	0.167	0.150	0.123
Panel (B) – Dependent Variable: Student Status					
Mental Health (After Start)	-0.220*** (0.033)	-0.218*** (0.044)	-0.187*** (0.042)	-0.193*** (0.045)	-0.224*** (0.050)
Mental Health (Before Start)	-0.039 (0.031)	-0.043 (0.043)	-0.044 (0.041)	-0.068 (0.047)	0.002 (0.042)
Observations	640	376	376	307	333
R-squared	0.104	0.107	0.154	0.134	0.149

Notes: Each column represents a separate regression. Columns (1), (4), and (5) control for ability with high school GPA. Column (2) uses SAT score. Column (3) uses both high school GPA and SAT score. Columns (1), (2), and (3) use the entire sample. Column (4) restricts the sample to students who began before the 2020 academic year. Column (5) restricts the sample to students who started in 2020 or 2021. All specifications include fixed effects for year/cohort and school. They also all include indicator variables for being local and for being international. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05 and * p<0.1.

Table 3 mirrors Table 2 but restricts the sample to those who do not report a mental health issue prior to beginning college. This addresses the concern that SAT score and high school GPA might not accurately measure ability if some students already suffered from mental health events while in high school. These estimates corroborate the results from Table 2: the coefficient on *Mental_Health* is large, negative, and highly statistically significant in both panels. The effect size is also larger for students who started college after the Covid-19 pandemic began.

Table 3: Impact of Any Mental Health Mention on Student Outcomes, Restricted Sample

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
				Before Covid	After Covid
Panel (A) – Dependent Variable: CCGPA					
Mental Health (After Start)	-0.189*** (0.050)	-0.133*** (0.051)	-0.111** (0.049)	-0.137*** (0.037)	-0.263** (0.105)
Observations	417	253	253	221	196
R-squared	0.100	0.073	0.147	0.199	0.115
Panel (B) – Dependent Variable: Student Status					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Mental Health (After Start)	-0.171*** (0.044)	-0.151*** (0.054)	-0.135** (0.052)	-0.143** (0.055)	-0.220*** (0.072)
Observations	376	231	231	198	178
R-squared	0.079	0.079	0.102	0.078	0.153

Notes: Each column represents a separate regression. *Columns (1), (4), and (5)* control for ability with high school GPA. *Column (2)* uses SAT score. *Column (3)* uses both high school GPA and SAT score. *Columns (1), (2), and (3)* use the entire sample. *Column (4)* restricts the sample to students who began before the 2020 academic year. *Column (5)* restricts the sample to students who started in 2020 or 2021. All specifications include fixed effects for year/cohort and school. They also all include indicator variables for being local and for being international. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$ and * $p < 0.1$.

5. Conclusions

The mental health of college students is a major concern, and its prevalence has grown substantially in recent years. Exploiting a unique dataset with information on student mental health both before and after starting college, this paper uses a fixed effect model to estimate the effect of mental health on college student outcomes. The evidence suggests that experiencing a mental health event during college has a large, statistically significant, and negative effect on CCGPA and the probability a student is in good standing with the university. Additionally, the effect size is larger for students who began after the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic, indicating this compounded the effect of mental health issues.

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